

LIFE OF A TEENAGER		Creative Writing Keywords: life, teenager, adolescence, bullying, anxiety, depression, youngsters, escape, control, victimization.
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Being a teenager is, in some respects, the most difficult stage of your life. This is the time in your life when you are attempting to define who you are, not only to others but also to yourself. Image, mental health, self-confidence, and a slew of other emotional issues plague us as teenagers. We live in a world where our lives are always changing. We appear to be interested in new things one minute and then dissatisfied with our existence the next. During this period of rapid development, teenagers seek to build their selves and interests. Teens go through a number of things that make them feel unimportant, and unloved. This is a normal aspect of adolescence. Your body is teasing you as the pressure grows on you to perform properly. You're angry one minute and crying the next and you have no idea why. Even if they are treated badly, teenagers aren't awkward and combative by choice. Bullying is a normal part of adolescence. Bullying occurs at all ages and in all settings, but the intensity of it during the school years may be horrific, and few people survive those years without feeling like a victim.

Teenage life is a roller coaster of emotions. You have highs and lows; one day you adore your life, the next you want to put it all behind you. We deal with a lot of mental health difficulties, which obviously has an impact on our happiness. This is the time of year when we must consider our future plans, which personally causes me a great deal of anxiety. Depression affects a large percentage of youngsters at some point in their lives. Treatment for adolescent depression, on the other hand, is frequently effective and helps youngsters cope with their mental stress and worry. When faced with stress and unfavorable circumstances, some teenagers turn to drugs as an escape from pain or a few situations over which they have no control. Victimization and seeing violence are the most typical reasons kids use drugs as a coping method.

We may lose friends at this time, which may be painful, but it is best to remove toxic people from our lives before it is too late.

I personally despise losing people I care about and in whom I have complete trust, but there are moments when you must let them go, even if it is excruciatingly painful.